

Adsorption of Binary Liquid Mixtures on Alumina

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Manuscript received 28 October 1973; accepted 9 April 1974

Adsorption from binary solutions of benzene and toluene with chlorobenzene and bromobenzene on alumina (neutral) has been investigated at 25°. The thermodynamic treatments outlined by Everett and Schay and Nagy have been extended to the adsorbed phase from these solutions. In most cases, results obtained by the alternate methods show a fair agreement. Differences are, however, observed in the activity coefficients of two components in the adsorbed phase.

THE theoretical analysis of the adsorbed layer when inert solids are equilibrated with binary mixtures has received considerable attention. However, the two main approaches namely of Schay and Nagy¹ and that of Everett² have rarely been compared. We therefore, considered it desirable to undertake this work with a view to determine adsorption of binary mixtures of benzene and toluene with chlorobenzene and bromobenzene on alumina and to study the results in the light of the two approaches. The components of these mixtures have nearly the same molecular cross-sectional areas and do not deviate significantly from Raoult's Law.

Experimental

The liquids have been purified according to standard procedures³ and their purity was checked by measuring densities at $25^\circ \pm 0.01^\circ$ which agreed to within $0.00002 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ with those given in the literature.

The adsorbent used was alumina (neutral) of unit activity supplied by National Physical Laboratories, Poona. It was dried at 110° for 72 hrs. Portions of 1.0 g of alumina were placed in glass ampoules and degassed for at least 30 hrs. The ampoules were then filled with about 7-8 ml of a binary solution of known composition, sealed and placed in a constant temperature water bath maintained at $25^\circ \pm 0.01^\circ$. The contents of these ampoules were allowed to equilibrate for 48 hrs or more with continuous stirring. The liquid phase was subsequently separated from the solid by centrifuging and the change in composition of the solution due to adsorption was determined, by an Abbe refractometer maintained at $25^\circ \pm 0.01^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

The experimental results are recorded in table 1. The composite adsorption isotherms for the four systems are shown in figures 1 and 2. It is observed

that in the system benzene (1)+chlorobenzene (2), chlorobenzene is preferred over the entire range of composition whereas in the system benzene (1)+bromobenzene (2), benzene is found to be the preferentially adsorbed component. In the system toluene (1)+chlorobenzene (2) and toluene (1)+bromobenzene (2), toluene is the component preferred over the whole range of composition.

We now consider our results in terms of the theories put forward by Everett¹² and Schay and Nagy¹. According to Kipling and Tester⁴ when a weight m of a solid is brought into contact with n_0 moles of a liquid, the mole fraction of the liquid decreases by Δx with respect to the component 1. This change in concentration is brought about by the transfer of n_1^σ moles of the component 1 and n_2^σ moles of the components 2 on the surface of a unit weight of the solid. At equilibrium, there remains in the liquid phase n_1^σ and n_2^σ moles respectively, of the two components, giving a mole fraction x with respect to component 1, the initial mole fraction being x_0 . Then

$$\frac{n_0 \Delta x}{m} = n_1^\sigma x_2 - n_2^\sigma x_1 \quad \dots (1)$$

The function $n_0 \Delta x / m$ on plotting against x , at equilibrium gives the composite adsorption isotherm which as such does not give true adsorption of any of the components.

Schay and Nagy¹ pointed out that some composite isotherms have a substantially linear section. Over such a section, the equation :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{n_0 \Delta x}{m} &= n_1^\sigma (1-x) - n_2^\sigma x \\ &= n_1^\sigma - (n_1^\sigma + n_2^\sigma)x \quad \dots (2) \end{aligned}$$

defines a straight line. Schay and Nagy consider that this is most probably due to n_1^σ and n_2^σ remaining constant over that section of the isotherm i.e.,

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Fig. 1-2. Composite Adsorption isotherms of Binary mixtures on Alumina.

△—Toluene(1) + Bromobenzene(2)

○—Benzene(1) + Chlorobenzene(2)

△—Benzene(1) + Chlorobenzene(2)

○—Toluene(1) + Chlorobenzene(2)

for a considerable range of x , the composition of adsorbed phase remains constant. This composition can be calculated if the linear section of the isotherm is extrapolated, giving values of n_1^σ , when $x = 0$ and n_2^σ when $x = 1$. Knowing these values, the surface area A of the solid is expressed as :

$$A = \left(\frac{n_1^\sigma}{m} \right) A_1 + \left(\frac{n_2^\sigma}{m} \right) A_2 \quad \dots (3)$$

where $A_i = (V^{2/3} N^{1/3})$ are the molecular occupancy of components ($i = 1, 2$) in the adsorbed phase, V is the molar volume and N is Avogadro number. The specific surface area A of the solid, thus determined, is taken as the BET area. The mole fraction in the adsorbed phase and the surface activity coefficients are then given by

$$x_i^\sigma = \frac{A x_i^l + A_2 (n_0 \Delta x_i^l / m)}{A + (A_2 - A_1) (n_0 \Delta x_i^l / m)} \quad \dots (4)$$

and

$$\ln \gamma_i^\sigma = \ln \gamma_i^l - \ln x_i^\sigma - (n_i - n) A_i / RT \quad \dots (5)$$

where n_i and n are in the interfacial tensions of the pure liquid and the solution and γ_i^σ and γ_i^l are the activity coefficients in the adsorbed and bulk phase respectively.

An alternative approach of calculating activity coefficients in the adsorbed phase has been given by Everett³. He has discussed the behaviour of a perfect solution in contact with a Langmuir type adsorbing surface. Accordingly, the mole fraction x_i^σ in the adsorbed phase can be obtained from the relation

$$\frac{n_0 \Delta x_1^l}{m} = \frac{n^\sigma}{m} (x_1^\sigma - x_1^l) \quad \dots (6)$$

where n_0 is the total number of moles of binary liquid mixture in equilibrium with m grams of the adsorbent, Δx_1^l is the change in the composition of component 1 due to adsorption, n_i^σ is the number of moles in the adsorbed phase and x_1^σ and x_1^l are

mole fractions of component 1 in the adsorbed phase (σ) and liquid phase (l) respectively. n^σ/m can be calculated from the relation :

$$\frac{x_1^l x_2^l}{n_0 \Delta x_1^l / m} = \frac{m}{n^\sigma} \left[x_1^l - \frac{1}{1 - K_a} \right] \quad \dots (7)$$

where K_a is the equilibrium constants for the process

$$(1)^\sigma + (2)^l \rightleftharpoons (1)^l + (2)^\sigma \quad \dots (8)$$

and is assumed to be independent of the composition. It is further assumed that the adsorption is of Langmuir type and that the ratio of activity coefficients $\frac{\gamma_1^l \gamma_2^\sigma}{\gamma_1^\sigma \gamma_2^l} \cong 1$. The surface activity coefficient of component 1 is given by :

$$\ln \gamma_1^\sigma = x_2^\sigma \ln \left[\frac{\gamma_1^l x_2^\sigma}{\gamma_2^l x_1^\sigma} \right] - \int_0^{x_2^\sigma} \ln \left(\frac{\gamma_1^l v_2^\sigma}{\gamma_2^l x_1^\sigma} \right) dx_2^\sigma \quad (9)$$

Taking equation (7), the values of K_a and n^σ/m can be calculated from the slope and intercept of the curve obtained by plotting

$$\frac{x_1^l x_2^l}{n_0 \Delta x_1^l / m} \text{ vs. } x_1^l.$$

Substituting those values in equation (6), x_1 can be calculated which on putting in (9) gives γ_1^σ . Similarly γ_2^σ can be calculated.

In all the isotherms, it is found that there is a considerable linear section so that the adsorbed layer can be analysed by the treatment given by Schay and Nagy¹. In evaluating $\ln \gamma_i^\sigma$ from expression (7) the surface tension data for the present systems was taken from the literature⁵. The activity coefficients in the liquid phase γ_i^l were calculated by fitting a Redlich-Kister type equation (6) to the available vapour liquid equilibrium data (7) of the system in the manner suggested by Lu and Lama⁸. The x_i^σ , n^σ/m , and $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$ values of this approach are recorded in Tables 2 and 3. The plots of $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$ vs x_i^σ are also shown in Figs. 3-6.

TABLE I. ADSORPTION—EQUILIBRUM DATA AT 25°

Benzene(1)+Chlorobenzene(2)			Benzene(1)+Bromobenzene(2)			Toluene(1)+Chlorobenzene			Toluene(1)+Bromobenzene(2)		
x_1^l	$\Delta x_1^l \times 10^2$	$(n_0 \Delta x_1^l / m) \times 10^4$	x_1^l	$\Delta x_1^l \times 10^2$	$(n_0 \Delta x_1^l / m) \times 10^4$	x_1^l	$\Delta x_1^l \times 10^2$	$(n_0 \Delta x_1^l / m) \times 10^4$	x_1^l	$\Delta x_1^l \times 10^2$	$(n_0 \Delta x_1^l / m) \times 10^4$
0.1066	-0.66	-0.39848	0.0869	1.09	6.6600	0.0713	1.72	10.2241	0.1040	0.12	0.9895
0.1782	-1.12	-0.60342	0.1991	1.41	8.3191	0.1529	1.71	10.3738	0.1464	0.22	1.3007
0.3281	-2.94	-0.19289	0.3268	1.17	7.3724	0.3181	1.55	8.7852	0.2354	0.28	1.8216
0.4306	-2.99	-1.60135	0.4076	0.96	6.3456	0.4018	1.12	7.4580	0.3552	0.32	2.0107
0.5201	-3.17	-1.99836	0.5576	0.78	4.6782	0.4885	1.28	6.6706	0.4055	0.31	1.9072
0.6223	-3.74	-2.45631	0.6348	0.48	3.4352	0.6501	0.75	4.1939	0.5799	0.21	1.2563
0.7176	-4.29	-2.70776	0.7336	0.36	2.3513	0.7439	0.60	3.1817	0.6677	0.17	0.9015
0.8417	-4.28	-3.00341	0.8511	0.14	0.8983	0.8225	0.39	2.1889	0.7250	0.15	0.6783
0.9369	-3.06	-1.95534	0.9293	0.08	0.4639	0.8770	0.33	1.5833	0.8355	0.05	0.2705

TABLE 2—ADSORPTION OF BINARY SOLUTIONS ON ALUMINA AT 25°. CONSTANTS FOR EQN. 3.

Benzene(1)+Chlorobenzene(2)				Benzene(1)+Bromobenzene(2)			
x_1^l	x_1^σ	$\log \gamma_1^\sigma$	$\log \gamma_2^\sigma$	x_1^l	x_1^σ	$\log \gamma_1^\sigma$	$\log \gamma_2^\sigma$
0.1066	0.0209	1.5891	0.2256	0.0869	0.6330	0.1700	0.0589
0.1782	0.0485	0.1616	0.1972	0.1991	0.8813	0.1521	0.6700
0.3281	0.0716	0.9311	0.1820	0.3268	0.9313	0.1773	0.9531
0.4306	0.0863	0.8188	0.1746	0.4076	0.9279	0.1750	0.9301
0.5201	0.0905	0.7855	0.1733	0.5575	0.9411	0.1835	1.0391
0.6223	0.0942	0.7596	0.1720	0.6348	0.9165	0.1672	0.8657
0.7176	0.1354	0.5671	0.1368	0.7336	0.9264	0.1724	0.9401
0.8417	0.2014	0.3577	0.1455	0.8511	0.9248	0.1706	0.9422
0.9369	0.5165	0.0630	0.2828	0.9293	0.9673	0.2047	1.3699
0.0713	0.8892	0.0475	0.7789	0.1040	0.2153	0.5814	-0.0413
0.1529	0.9828	0.1185	1.6990	0.1464	0.2927	0.4098	-0.0305
0.3181	—	—	—	0.2354	0.4403	0.1958	0.0407
0.4018	0.9984	0.1443	2.7667	0.3532	0.5794	0.0856	0.0860
0.4885	—	—	—	0.5799	0.7212	0.0330	0.3785
0.6561	0.9916	0.1314	2.0163	0.6667	0.7681	0.0291	0.4758
0.7439	0.9984	0.1942	2.7522	0.7250	0.8013	0.0307	0.5576
0.8225	0.9976	0.1425	2.5742	0.8355	0.8659	0.0432	0.7633
0.8770	—	—	—	0.8732	0.8901	0.0521	0.8659

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$ vs. X_i^σ for the system benzene (1) + Chlorobenzene (2) on Alumina.

O—Schay and Nagy values
 Δ—Everett values

In order to find Everett's value, $\frac{x_1^l x_2^l}{n_0 \Delta x_1^l / m}$ is plotted against x_1^l for the systems (Figs. 7-10). For the systems studied here, the linear relationship is followed upto the mole fraction $\cong 0.6$ of the preferentially adsorbed component. However, as a first approximation n^σ may be estimated from equation (7) neglecting the deviation from the perfect behaviour. x_i^σ , n^σ/m and $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$ values calculated in this manner are recorded in Tables 2 and 3 and $\frac{x_1^l x_2^l}{n_0 \Delta x_1^l / m}$ values are tabulated in Table 4.

Columns (iii) and (v) of Table 2 show that there is a good agreement of n^σ/m values between the approaches of Everett and that of Schay and Nagy. However, Table 3 reveals that except for the system toluene + bromobenzene, the Everett's expression yields values which are higher than the corresponding Nagy's values for the more preferentially adsorbed component. Nevertheless, the agreement is fairly

Figs. 4-5. Plots of $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$ vs. X_i^σ for Alumina.

System :
Benzene(1) + Bromobenzene(2)

System :
Toluene(1) + Chlorobenzene(2)

good between the two sets of values. The divergence between the two approaches is best seen by comparing the $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$ values, which are defined in both approaches as : $x_i^\sigma \rightarrow 1$ as $\gamma_i^\sigma \rightarrow 1$. However, in going from x_i^σ to $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$, Everett equation (9) assumes that K_a is independent of the composition, and does not need a prior estimation of A_i as is required in Schay and Nagy's equation (5). In addition, some differences may be expected from the last term

composition range upto $x_i^\sigma \cong 0.5$ and then changing abruptly. However, in this system, the $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$ values for the less preferentially adsorbed component also remain constant over a considerable range upto $x_i^\sigma \cong 0.7$ and there is an abrupt change. In toluene + bromobenzene system, the range upto which the constancy of $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$ values for the preferentially adsorbed component is observed is narrower ($x_i^\sigma \cong 0.2$) after which there is an abrupt change. Here again for the less adsorbed component, $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$ values decrease gradually. Keeping in view, the assumptions involved in Everett equation (7) and the uncertainties induced by graphical integration, it is difficult to rely on $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$ values. Nevertheless the similarity of their trends for the adsorption from four different binary solutions on alumina is notable.

FIG 6 PLOT OF $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$ VS X_i^σ FOR THE SYSTEM TOLUENE (1) + BROMOBENZENE (2) ON ALUMINA

of expression (9) which involves graphical integration of different variables and renders the process somewhat less accurate.

In considering Everett's $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$ values as a function of x_i^σ we note that for the systems benzene + chlorobenzene and benzene + bromobenzene, the $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$ values for the preferentially adsorbed component remain constant over a considerable range of $x_i^\sigma \cong 0.7$ and then there is a sudden rise in its values (Figs. 3 and 4). On the other hand for the less preferentially adsorbed component, $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$ values decrease regularly with x_i^σ . The same trend is followed to toluene + chlorobenzene, the value being constant over a

The $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$ values calculated from Schay and Nagy's expression (5) are considerably higher than the corresponding Everett values for the less preferentially adsorbed component except in system toluene + chlorobenzene (Fig. 5). Also whereas Everett values show constancy of $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$ values over a considerable composition range, Schay and Nagy values indicate no such behaviour and $\log \gamma_i^\sigma$ values decrease regularly with x_i^σ for the preferentially as well as the less preferentially adsorbed components in these mixtures. Similar observations were made by Suri and Ramakrishna⁹.

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